

Policlicks: Filipino values reflected on viral political issues in social media

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Abstract

In the midst of the current digital age, the appearance of viral political issues is becoming more common on social media, especially in the Philippines wherein political disarray and debacles are present. This study was conducted with the intent of thoroughly analyzing such issues and the Filipino values put into practice. In order to acquire information, three (3) viral political issues have gone through the qualitative process of content analysis--namely, #SEAGamesFail, Sen. Cynthia Villar on rising prices of commodities, and Sen. Bato Dela Rosa's visa cancellation. To organize gained data, a coding form was utilized for this study. During this endeavor, it has been found that Filipino values that surface in these issues tend to become biased against the lower class and focus on the resignation of effort. This paper also discusses the following findings on certain aspects: politicians show Filipino values through passing work to someone else; netizens portray their Filipino values through defending, caring, and becoming concerned towards victims and themselves, and the prominent Filipino values are utilized as the base point for the understanding of the public towards the issue. This study investigated the topics chosen within the terms of action (politicians), reaction (netizens), and message validation. To define its importance, the study will serve as a basis for the understanding of certain patterns present in Filipino culture in relation to stands and biases on the viral political issues on social media which can be beneficial towards social media users, news organizations, politicians, psychologists, society, and future researchers.

Keywords: *Social media users; News organizations; Action; Reaction; Viral political issues.*

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Introduction

The society we live in thrives in an age of information, which heavily relies on various platforms. Social media is one of the most widely used, accessible, and powerful platforms of our day and age. Based on the study of Usman (2015), it shows that social media is an effective way to disseminate information due to its easy access and wide range of forms and styles of posting. Thus, it encourages people to create interactions, share content, and, most importantly, give updates on the happenings in our daily lives. This allows even the most trivial people to capture moments that may seem meager, but when posted online, may spark controversy, buzz, and abrupt popularity due to the massive differences in the perspectives of the internet population.

In research done by Phelps et al. (2004), online mail is forwarded when emotions are appealing to others. They also found out that in the positive spectrum, contents that make people feel good, happy, excited, and connected are more likely to be sent once more, while negative emotions such as skepticism, irritation, anger, and disappointment are also shared with other people but with reservation. This may mirror the common social media habits up until today, wherein users share content that resonates and is relevant to personal aspects of their lives.

The concept of emotion, including several other factors, introduces the possibility of values, specifically Filipino values, being portrayed online on social media platforms. This is due to the fact that the values of a specific culture affect how a person handles situations in the aspects of thinking, emotional expression, and conflict resolution (Rungduin & Rungduin, 2013). In the case of this study, Filipino values can influence the perception, reaction, and certain moves that a person takes. Their understanding of the topics at hand may vary depending on the values they exude. Filipinos, by nature, have a long list of values or traits that merge with their identity, but all are based on the concept of contributions to society.

In congruence with the involvement of values, the existence of viral political issues becomes a ground for the portrayal of values. Viral political issues often contain failures, threats, and satirical instances that allow the public to have a grasp on the level of the issue and the intensity of emotions to be felt in order to produce a reaction. In order to do that, one must put his or her values to the test and apply such traits. The controversy surrounding the viral political issue heightens the sense of urgency due to the presence of Filipino values, which allows the netizens to take their stand on the issue and show their values.

Due to the rise of this phenomenon, it is a positive indicator that researchers need to investigate the current situation of social media issues, specifically viral political issues. Its focus is the determination of Filipino values reflected in the said issues on social media platforms.

Theoretical / Conceptual Framework

Issues shared on viral media usually gain responses from involved and concerned people, which stem from the emotional and/or personal relevance of the issue. The more people connect with the issue, the more widely it spreads. This is supported by Berger (2013), in which he discussed that there are six factors that need to be acknowledged in order for something to become viral, and one of those is emotion—a vital part for content to become shareable.

Similarly, political issues seem to gather negative emotions wherever they are placed, be it in the real world or social media. As an assumption based on current information, there must be similarities in the content of viral political issues on social media due to their tendency to gather a reach among the online population. In the works of Quito (1994), she illustrated that Filipino values have positive and negative sides but revolve around the concepts of laziness or resignation of effort towards work.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the reflected Filipino values in viral political issues on social media. More specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the Filipino values reflected in the viral political issues on social media?
2. How do the Filipino values show in viral political issues on social media in terms of action and reaction?
3. How do the Filipino values validate the message portrayed by the viral political issue on social media?

Literature Review

Political Use of Social Media

In order to see the bigger picture, research allows us to get the pieces and the details in order to form a better understanding of the topic. In this case, the study of Pertierra (2012) tells us that politics, specifically in the Philippines, appear to be undisturbed and unchanging, but due to new media coming in and becoming the go-to of the majority, the “notions of the political” are adapting and changing, wherein the global influence of social media also plays a part. In the same study, it stated that the Philippines bears traces of its past, ignoring the test of time, for its politics are traditional, its culture is modern, and its media is postmodern. So it is safe to assume that the population, along with its media, is critical toward the government due to the slow progress of change promised by numerous people before them.

This world’s society has advanced technologically, resorting to more convenient methods more often, and social media is not an exception. The platform has numerous factors that allow the spread of information—specifically, ones with political tropes. In the article of Fonbuena (2013), which tackled the concepts of politics and social media as a tool for influence, he stated that when the said platform “gains dominance” over national television, then it has the potential to effectively sway people’s opinions regarding government situations.

As of this year, we have seen the transition from television to social media in terms of information literacy. Variations in opinions needed to be catered to as well, and not only focusing on pro-poor imagery and platforms such as Facebook allowed these kinds of approaches, but candidates are also ready to utilize this playing field (Rappler, 2019). Taking these into account, political issues and accomplishments were gradually becoming a tool in order for the perspectives of the online mass to take sides, which then may become an advantage when it comes to the elections.

A good example of a political icon using this strategy is Dr. Willie Ong, a former senatorial candidate. An article by Castro (2019) illustrated that he focused on online presence rather than traditional presence, which led him to be the most followed on Instagram and have the highest number of shared posts compared to other candidates. Although with an impeccable digital record, in the same article, Dr. Willie Ong’s presence online did not convert to votes as expected, only gaining a 57% awareness rate (Pulse Asia). Though not effective in elections, political issues have the power to go viral and start to make a change.

In the recent SEA Games 2019 event, there has been a fiasco and complications are starting to show, and netizens picked up on the information and started sharing it, predominantly on Twitter and Facebook (#SEAGamesFail). There, things went viral and immediately became political, for countries such as Timor-Leste arrived but received drab and unlikely accommodation. To add to that, buildings were still in progress, the quality of welcome tarpaulins and directions was not on par with the budget, and the mobile app was unpolished and basic (Alabaso, 2019; Rappler, 2019).

This resulted in a pointing of fingers, a breakdown of costs, and an urge to act now or die in shame led by social media users, which made the issue viral and, thankfully, reached the higher-ups and started to address the problems. As shown by the opening and the various polished facilities, it did make a change (Murillo, 2019).

Virality

According to Berger (n.d.), social media is great. Social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn have made communication for everyone easier and faster. Only 7% of word-of-mouth happens online. In addition, social media is the most effective medium of communication bilaterally over the Internet. Facebook is a platform of choice for a variety of purposes, such as communication with family and friends, developing or establishing businesses, and spreading the influence of ideology to attract more followers (Zanuddin & Hidayah, 2019). This introduces the concept of virality.

In a study by Al-Rawi (2019), viral news is defined as networked news stories that spread online, mostly through social media, in a much faster and wider manner than other news stories. Virality is partially driven by physiological arousal. Content that evokes high-arousal positive (awe) or negative (anger or anxiety) emotions is more viral. Content that evokes low-arousal, or deactivating, emotions (e.g., sadness) is less viral (Berger & Milkman, 2012). In order for content to go viral online, there are characteristic features that it should contain. Social currency is one factor that is of high value in making a person's information shareable. Triggers are defined as something simple to remember about a brand, idea, or product in order to make it maximally stick to people's memory. Another factor is the emotion that a post evokes in its audience. Publicity here concerns the product or the idea that should be shown to people to spread among them. Practical value talks about the practicality and applicability of content. Lastly, story refers to stories told in order for users to get more connected to a post (Berger, 2013). In congruency with the notion of emotion, there was a time when Filipino netizens saw an opportunity where they could spark change and spread the word regarding political issues while keeping close to the hearts of fellow countrymen.

According to the findings of Calimbo (2016), humor is one of the ways Filipinos express political views on issues online, being critical and aggressive while making the politically elite, their power, and their actions satirical, which leads to fellow users gaining awareness and therefore starts a cycle of sharing and spreading throughout the lifespan of the post. Due to this habit, political constructs are becoming normalized in the country's society. All in all, the study expresses that Filipino online humor has the capability to show the ills of the political situation in a light and absorbable way for the majority of the population. As a whole, the texts have presented the importance of emotions in creating a phenomenon, which is, as said earlier, virality, which is the potential of an online item to spread far and wide.

Exploitation of Virality

There are people who take advantage of patterns and try to spread misinformation and push their political agenda, the total opposite of what the internet humor originally stood for, and in the research of Ong and Cabañes (2018), they were called the architects of networked disinformation, which are in essence teams of internet people with influence and a handful of fake account operators whose tasks are to execute the needs of certain industries and promote their cause, which usually has underlying negative causes.

This is supported by another study done by Soriano and Sreekumar (2012), wherein they found out that social media is a tool in political discourse that can change the knowledge of the masses regarding the issue, specifically the Moro National Liberation Front. All in all, this shows that political issues are embezzled with the possibility of being engineered to go viral and to encourage the online masses to create a reaction or think the same as they do.

Social Media Habits and Journalism

We now have all the information we need at the touch of an app, and most people now get their news information online, specifically from social media. Social media has become the main source of news online, with more than 2.4 billion internet users; nearly 64.5 percent receive breaking news from Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Snapchat, and Instagram instead of traditional media (Martin, 2018). According to a Forbes survey, 50 percent of Internet users surveyed said that they hear about the latest news via social media before ever hearing about it on a news station. Many internet users will see breaking stories on their feed and go to the news sites to learn more. However, there has been a decrease in the number of articles that people read. Most people will just scroll through their newsfeed and stumble upon relevant news content, then read the headlines or a short video clip of the piece. An average visitor will only read an article for 15 seconds or less, and the average video watch time online is 10 seconds. Due to these trends, there has been a decline in demand for newspapers, and there has been an observed rise in the usage of television and online news sites in cooperation with social media (Haselton, 2018). Based on the same article, they have found that in the US, people find social media to be more reliable and accessible and have disregarded, though not totally, the newspaper.

These social media habits have molded how the news industry should move and write in the past few years and what steps they should take in order to take advantage of these new findings. This has led them to change their style of writing to match the attention span of the online mass, boiling everything down to digestible chunks with visually invoking fact-filled texts (Naeem et al., 2021). In addition to the earlier notion, journalism has become dependent on what social media has to say regarding an issue or a specific topic of interest, thus making them reliant on popular online personalities when it comes to what they will write. This is due to the fact that these well-known icons will serve as a support for their arguments and a conduit to spread such information throughout the platform. But this leads to the phenomenon wherein journalists are forced to write about certain “in” topics with catchy short headlines that present themselves as unavoidable. Although mentioned earlier as a negative aspect, the community, as a whole, has accepted and is continuously learning how to move on the digital platform and has normalized its use in gauging what to write and when to write (Journalism Research News, 2018).

Filipino Values

Citizens of the Philippines portray a wide range of habits and beliefs that strengthen and justify the identity established and the perception created towards themselves. Although numerous traits can be listed, they all boil down to two simple concepts that serve as the foundation of their complexities: *loob* (relational will) and *kapwa* (together with the person) (Reyes, 2015). Based on the same study, these serve as the pillars for values that focus on interpersonal matters and outward interactions rather than self-improvement and internal consultation. This creates a cycle wherein instead of individualizing oneself, he or she sets a mentality where he or she is indifferent to her “*kapwa*” (others) and is expected to become altruistic. Although positive outcomes usually ensue, it is seen not to be from the intent of altruism but instead from the recognition and benefits.

As for another point of view, Filipino values are separated into categories in the study of Yacat (2013), which are: accommodative surface value, confrontational surface value, pivotal interpersonal value, linking socio-personal value, and associated sociocultural values. All of which contain values that resonate with the theme of their category and values that show respect for the core concepts. In another light, this form of value, along with their accompanied habits and traits, all come together to enable Filipinos to become good leaders who promote harmony, establish close relationships with peers and subordinates, and, perception-wise, decentralize authority (Torres, 1985).

Though there are still negative values as opposed to the overall goodness of the components of Filipino values, There are values such as *hiya*, *ningas cogon*, and many more, but they are all based on the concept that success comes naturally and without the exertion of effort (Quito, 1994). There is also the *padrino* system, which is referred to as the trait that can be used to “game the system” (Bailey et al., 2018), and a form of inconsideration called *matapobre*, which is defined by Leoncini (2005) as disliking towards the lower class. Therefore, supporting negativity and giving focus to laziness and resignation in efforts were instead considered.

Synthesis

All in all, the research and the texts collected and analyzed indeed contain some supporting evidence to support the research that will be conducted. They strengthen the notion that technology paves a way for users to create an environment wherein emotions, as shown by studies done by Berger and Milkman (2012), Calimbo (2016), and others listed, are the key to making things spread in the digital world. As emphasized in the study of Calimbo, humor is one emotion that makes social issues, specifically political issues, circulate.

Other resources used seem to suggest that social media has indeed proven these findings, wherein articles contain all the buzz, such as a candidate’s certain effort to dominate the digital arena, which is elaborated in the works of Dado (2019), and that the studies talk about how political issues are engineered to be spread at certain points by professionals who know their craft well enough (Ong & Cabañes, 2018).

To add to that, Quito (1994) set out a list wherein she illustrated that Filipino values are all about laziness and lack of effort, which is congruent with the common content of political issues. Other authors, such as Bailey et al. (2018) and Leoncini (2005), contribute to the collection of Filipino values being defined because, in their findings, Filipino values such as *matapobre* and the *Padrino* system are given a clearer meaning.

The above literature reviews seem to support the notion that human emotional responses to the content of a certain political topic can affect the virality of many political issues, up to the point of being exploited due to the patterns that are likely to be seen. In continuation, due to the virality and the presence of an emotional response, Filipino values start to surface in many aspects of the topic.

Methodology

Research Method

This study will utilize the content analysis method of qualitative research to ascertain selected viral political issues present on social media. The method chosen is deemed appropriate since the study will focus on the in-depth analysis of Filipino values in certain viral political issues. Data for this endeavor will be collected from the three (3) selected political issues that have gone viral on social media.

Sources of Data

For this research, data will mainly be sourced from the three (3) selected viral political issues in social media: (1) #SEAGamesFail, (2) Sen. Cynthia Villar on rising prices, and (3) Sen. Bato Dela Rosa’s visa cancellation. Resources focusing on such topics will be utilized, while concepts rooted in related literature will be considered secondary data to support this research.

Research Instrument

The researchers will gather data through a thorough analysis of the various articles in social media related to viral political issues, which will be organized systematically using a coding form. The compiled data from the three (3) selected viral political issues in social media will then be used to form the results of the study.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers proposed a research problem tackling the viral political issues that are present on social media. When approved, the researchers would then collect the necessary resources related to the three (3) selected viral political issues on social media in preparation for analysis. Once sources are set, thorough analysis will be of high priority, with complete regard to detail, in order to interpret such concepts and identify factors related to Filipino values present in viral political issues on social media.

Data Analysis

The researchers would determine the Filipino values reflected on selected viral political issues on social media. These aspects were looked into comprehensively and with great caution in order to attain true results. The actions of the politicians involved and the reactions of the netizens to the viral political issues were considered for analysis.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Filipino values reflected in the viral political issues (#SEAGamesFail)

Filipino Values	Statements/Article Snippets/Headlines
“Bahala Na” Attitude	<i>Walang pintura, may scaffolding set-up pa sa press room para sa football, kahit may mga nangyayari nang football games sa kasalukuyan.</i> (There is no paint; there are still scaffolds in the press room for football, yet there are football games that are currently going.)
Inconsideration	Non-halal food in the meals that were served them... A Muslim media officer with the Indonesian Men’s Football Team was disappointed with the 30th SEA Games organizers because their failure to make a distinction between halal and non-halal food in the meals that were served them had caused him to eat pork accidentally.

#SEAGamesFail has become a major issue as it involves poor facilities and unpreparedness encountered by foreign countries competing in the homeland. These series of failures have become examples of some values that are already imprinted in Filipino culture. To support the values found, *bahala na* is clearly seen in the issue because, according to Quito (1994), it is the resignation from duties and leaving things as is, and that is what the first headline states, for the pressroom was presented, but it was unfinished. Inconsideration stems from having something else to prioritize, thus rushing and paying no heed to the certain needs of a situation, similar to the situation in the second headline, as it shows cultural insensitivity caused by inconsideration.

Table 2. Filipino values reflected in the viral political issues (Sen. Cynthia Villar on rising prices of commodities)

Filipino Values	Statements/Article Snippets/Headlines
Inconsideration (Matapobre)	Villar on higher <i>galunggong</i> prices: Why eat it if too expensive?
Passivity	Instead of importing <i>galunggong</i> , patronize other local catch - Senate of the Philippines

Shown in this issue are vast amounts of idiotic inconsideration as Senator Cynthia Villar, who is supposed to manage agriculture, looks at the situation from her elitist point of view. This is seen as “*matapobre*,” which is defined by Leoncini (2005) as a person who disregards or dislikes the lower class. Her stand on the price hikes, as seen in the headlines, seems passive because her statements focus on using alternatives present in the market and putting the weight on the consumers rather than implementing an effective, sound, and plausible course of action in order to stabilize the prices. All of these are done while ignoring the fact that *galunggong* (blue mackerel scad) has been a staple food on the dining tables of Filipinos for several decades.

Table 3. Filipino values reflected in the viral political issues (Sen. Bato Dela Rosa's visa cancellation)

Filipino Values	Statements/Article Snippets/Headlines
Padrino System (Pardoner)	BREAKING: President Rody Duterte said he is giving the US government one month to reverse its cancellation of Senator Bato Dela Rosa’s visa.
Lakas Loob (Oversensitivity)	JUST IN. Following the United States' decision to cancel the visa of Senator Ronald "Bato" dela Rosa, President Rodrigo Duterte renewed his threats to "terminate" the Philippines' Visiting Forces Agreement with the US. - President Rodrigo Duterte
	Senator dela Rosa doesn’t give a f**k about his canceled US visa.

As shown in the headlines, prominent in this issue is the presence of political favors and an unnecessary amount of aggression. On surface value, it can be seen that the President is “defending” the former Philippine National Police (PNP) Chief, but the situation somehow portrays the practice of the Padrino system, while the hostile threats show signs of the “*lakas loob*” trait due to the ludicrous demands made. The imprinted oversensitivity of the Filipinos when it comes to certain issues can also be shown in the same action, as the former PNP Chief and now Senator does not care about his visa. Evidence is the concept of resignation of effort found in the work of Quito (1994), in the sense that Duterte will not exert effort to bend and properly address the issue with regards to the rules.

Table 4. Filipino values reflected in terms of action (#SEAGamesFail)

Filipino Values	Actions/Descriptions of Situations
Blaming Others	“It was Senator Drilon who moved the budget of the SEA Games to the PSC (Philippine Sports Commission), and it was Senator Drilon who proposed cutting it by 33%...” – Senator Alan Peter Cayetano
Hiya	<i>Sa mga foreign teams, talagang</i> we are apologizing (To our foreign teams, we are really apologizing) for the inconveniences or if I may call it inefficiencies or miscoordination.

There are many political figures that can be included in this issue, but mostly, it revolves around Senator Alan Peter Cayetano, the appointed head of this event, and his publicized actions. Filipinos rarely back down when it comes to pointing fingers, and the actions of the politicians clearly show that they are no exception to Cayetano’s statement. He is clearly putting the blame on others, specifically Senator Franklin Drilon, due to his meddling with the Southeast Asian (SEA) Games budget. In the financial chaos, Filipinos are known to pretend things are fine and try their best to still accommodate their guests, a trait that is seen in the action of Senator Cayetano. He apologizes for the unpreparedness the country has shown and states that an effort will be made to make up for the mishap. Evident in this action is the outward interaction and the inclusion of better treatment of *kapwa*, a concept shown in the study of Reyes (2015), with *kapwa* being the foreign competitor.

Table 5. Filipino values reflected in terms of reaction (#SEAGamesFail)

Filipino Values	Reactions/Comments and Related Posts
Hiya	Dear Cambodia, Myanmar, Thailand, We are sorry that it’s not so fun in the Philippines after all. We apologize that your teams got a shabby welcome for the 2019 SEA Games. Our government is corrupt. Sincerely, The Filipino People
Compassion	<i>Nagkaisa ang Filipino netizens sa pagpapalakas ng loob sa mga atleta ng Timor-Leste para sa SEA Games.</i> (Filipino netizens are united in supporting Timor-Leste's athletes for the SEA Games.) Timor-Leste, just rejoice and enjoy the games whatever happens. We, Filipinos love you. You can do it! God bless you all!

Similar to the actions of the politicians, the Filipinos expressed their plea for pardons for the incompetence shown by their country. Ashamed and apologetic of the happenings, the mass extended their hospitality by posting comments and statuses regarding the issue while adding context as to why the venues look so grim and unpolished. Since the games began and the results started to roll in, Timor-Leste has plunged to the bottom of the rankings. Though competitive Filipinos may be, Timor-Leste received love and support from the Philippines as netizens and crowds cheered and wished for their success. This is where social currency comes into play. Based on the works of Jonah Berger in 2013, reactions like these are commonplace due to their capacity to influence the perception of their online connections and present their online identity. In this case, people shared this topic due to their need to show that they, as people of the Philippines, want to show their feelings of encouragement.

Table 6. Filipino values reflected in terms of action (Sen. Cynthia Villar on rising prices of commodities)

Filipino Values	Actions/Descriptions of Situations
Inconsideration (<i>Matapobre</i>)	<i>Kung mahal ang galunggong, eh di wag kumain ng galunggong, 'di ba?</i> (If a blue mackerel scad is expensive, don't eat that fish, right?) There are other alternatives.... <i>Bakit ba gustong-gusto 'nyo 'yung galunggong kung mahal ang galunggong?</i> (Why do you like this blue mackerel scad so much if this is expensive?) – Senator Cynthia Villar
Blaming Others	<i>Gustong-gusto nila mag-import. May naglalakad pa sa akin na bigyan daw sila ng import permit sa galunggong. Bakit ba patay na patay tayo?</i> (People want to import. Someone asks me to give them an import permit for the fish. Why are we so being impatient?) – Senator Cynthia Villar

In this case, Senator Cynthia Villar’s actions are clear signs of putting the blame on another identity, which is that of Filipino citizens. As shown in her statement, she throws the heat of the issue towards the people who are actually actively trying to find a solution to counter her passivity towards the hike. Unsurprisingly, it can be seen that this is another scheme in order to avoid another workload, thus proving the concept of the resignation of effort of Quito (1994).

Table 7. Filipino values reflected in terms of reaction (Sen. Cynthia Villar on rising prices of commodities)

Filipino Values	Reactions/Comments and Related Posts
Inconsideration	<p><i>Kumbaga, kapag maiksi ang kumot, matutong mamaluktot. Kaya mahal yan kasi mataas demand at dahil alam nilang parating ang Xmas bonus. (When a blanket is short, learn to bend. That's why it's expensive because demands are getting high and because they know the Christmas bonus is coming.)</i></p> <p><i>Bakit daming galit? Totoo naman. Kung mahal ang isang bagay ipipilit mo bang ibaba presyo nun para maafford mo? (Why is there so much anger? It's true. If something is expensive, will you insist on lowering its price so that you can afford it?) Choose something else! Susme! (My goodness!)</i></p> <p><i>Ang isang bagay, kung di mo kerin na bilihin, wag kang bumili. Kasi mahal! Ang galunggong kung sobra na talaga sa mahal, bakit ka bibili? Hayaan mo siyang mabilasa at mabulok! Ang Pilipinas ay naliligiran ng tubig na napakalawak ng karagatan. Bakit umabot sa ganyan kamahal ang mga isda? (One thing, if you can't afford to buy it, don't buy it. Because it's expensive! If the fish is really too expensive, why would you buy it? Let it rot and rot! The Philippines is surrounded by water that is as vast as the ocean. Why are those fishes so expensive?)</i></p>
Pakikisama	<p><i>May point naman kasi si Villar. Bakit ipagpipilitan mo kumain ng galunggong kung marami namang mas murang isda? Dahil mahal yung galunggong, naging matumal, kinahapunan ibinaba uli ng mga tindera ang presyo para lang mabili. Di naman nakakamatay kung di kakain ng galunggong kahit isang taon pa. (Villar has a point. Why would you insist on eating that blue mackerel scad when there are many cheaper fishes? Because that fish was expensive, so much that it became sluggish; in the evening, the vendors lowered the price again just to buy it. It's not deadly if you don't eat this kind of fish even for one more year.)</i></p>

There have been a lot of buzz and reactions regarding the actions of Villar. Some people share the same point of view as Senator Cynthia Villar, thus strengthening the traits of inconsideration towards the *kapwa* as well as showing *pakikisama*, a trait listed in the works of Quito (1994) which has the quality wherein people close their eyes and just go with the flow. In addition to this, Filipinos love power and therefore, use this issue as a ground to gain attention and in general become *epals*. There are also hints of hypocrisy in such statements where the situation is not fully understood. In this situation, the same factor of successful virality dominates the issue, which is social currency (Berger, 2013). People comment on the posts related to their needs for something that will present and support their ideals regarding the issue. Based on the information, the posts give people a way to actively show their sympathy and call for action.

Table 8. Filipino values reflected in terms of action (Sen. Bato Dela Rosa's visa cancellation)

Filipino Values	Actions/Descriptions of Situations
Mañana habit	<p><i>“Titingnan ko kung pupunta si Presidente Duterte sa kanyang invitation ni Trump, just in case pupunta siya at pasasamahin niya ako do’n, then I will apply. (I’ll see if President Duterte will go to his invitation of Donald Trump just in case he will go and take me there, then I will apply.)”</i></p> <p>- Sen. Bato Dela Rosa</p>
Padrino (Pardoner)	<p><i>“Si Bato, ayaw nila papuntahin sa Amerika. (Bato, they don't want to go to America.) I am warning you; this is the first time. ‘Pag hindi ninyo ginawa ang correction diyan (If you don't make the correction there), one, I will terminate the bases, the Visiting Forces Agreement. Tapusin ko ‘yang p— ina (I’ll finish that f***ing thing),”</i></p> <p>- President Rodrigo Duterte</p>

There are two persons of focus here: the President, the one who plays the role of pardoner, and Senator Ronald Dela Rosa, the one who is being pardoned. President Rodrigo Duterte continues on making demands and spewing vulgarity, while the former PNP Chief has shown signs of the manana habit, wherein he sends out a message, “*Why do I need to do it today when the president does not have an urgent need?*” Thus, invalidating and putting Duterte’s efforts in vain. As stated before, this issue focuses on Quito’s concept of resignation and stubbornness to exert effort. Pardoning revolves around this concept for status and position are used in order to bypass certain processes that are stated and set in stone.

Table 9. Filipino values reflected in terms of reaction (Sen. Bato Dela Rosa's visa cancellation)

Filipino Values	Reactions/Comments and Related Posts
Fun-loving	<i>Dapat ang caption ng mga news about Duts</i> (I think Duterte’s news captions were like), from now on [he] is “The President of Renewed Words” <i>kesyo threat, kesyo pagmumura, pagkucurse sa mga obispo, pagreresign, over used ‘I hate drugs, I hate corruptions,’ eh paulit ulit na lang</i> (whether he’s threatening, cursing the people even the bishops, resigning, keeps on saying 'I hate drugs, I hate corruptions,' it’s becoming redundant.)
Makabayan	To Malacañang, please respect my country’s sovereignty.

Based on the comments, the Filipinos are divided on what these issues mean to them. Some make them a mockery or find humor in them, making it a light event that will pass by. Others view it as a trampling and dishonoring of the Filipino country’s established society and civilization. Netizens type words with intense emotions of fury and anger, along with their analysis of the situation and their take on proper courses of action. This is done with effort in order to somehow patronize and defend the Philippines from such a threat, thus showing the *makabayan* trait in their blood as Filipinos. As shown by the information above, virality is successfully achieved due to the issue touching on the aspect of practical value (Berger, 2013). The netizens react due to the fact that this can affect their daily lives in terms of physical and economic stability.

Table 10. Validation of the Filipino values towards the message of viral political issues (#SEAGamesFail)

Filipino Values	Observations/Related Texts
“Bahala na” Attitude	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We live in a clownery. • The "P" in Duterte administration means preparedness. • Well he's technically not wrong. • We've come very far. Just not in the right direction.

In light of this issue, Filipino traits and values, mainly the *bahala na* attitude, as defined by Quito (1994) as the act of just letting things be, have supported and influenced the view of the public regarding the issue on social media. The *bahala na* attitude plays a role in instigating criticism from the mass by feeding them with incomplete and disappointing low-effort products, which are the venues and accommodations in this case, with the mindset of anti-proactivity.

As shown in their responses, they mock the administration for settling such inferior quality of construction and poor planning of the event through sarcastic remarks and short punchlines in the context of the issue. This is assumed to be possible due to the factor of social currency (Berger, 2013) coming into the picture, as it allows angry and compassionate netizens to show the online platform what they feel and how they connect with the issue.

Table 11. Validation of the Filipino values towards the message of viral political issues (Sen. Cynthia Villar on rising prices of commodities)

Filipino Values	Observations/Related Texts
Inconsideration (<i>Matapobre</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Yung bigas na lang ang paangkat mo ng paangkat para yung magsasaka matuwa sa 'yo.</i> (More rice shall be imported so that the farmers might be happy with you.) • Wow! What an intelligent proposal! • <i>Ang tanong diyan, mura ba ang gulay?</i> (The question is, are vegetables cheaper?) • <i>Kulang na taniman kase ginawa mo pong subdivision.</i> (There is not enough land because you converted this into a subdivision.)

Primarily seen in this issue is a trait of some Filipinos, which is being inconsiderate. Villar's *matapobre* aura and elite status in life and politics solidify and heighten the prominence of the said trait. Her view on the situation makes her the star of the issue. Shown in her acts is her being reluctant to become proactive and exert effort, which is, once again, a concept of reluctance and resignation illustrated in the work of Quito (1994).

This has led netizens to become very critical of Senator Cynthia Villar's decision-making. Viral posts to her have been bombarded with an assortment of comments, but more commonly with the themes of sarcasm, play on words, and regional comparison. To sum up, the value presented helps the message get through to people, but with intense emotions due to the lower-class netizens' sense of practicality with the issue.

Table 12. Validation of the Filipino values towards the message of viral political issues (Bato Dela Rosa's visa cancellation)

Filipino Values	Observations/Related Texts
Padrino System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDS (Diehard Duterte Supporters), be proud of your president. Most of the times, he puts his interest and that of his men over the interest of the people. Really a president you could be proud and die for. Call on all your gods and pray to them for him because the One True God will not listen. He will only listen if he himself bends down on his knees and ask for forgiveness. • The driver of your decision Mr. President is not the Filipino people. The driver is your personal relationship with Bato and the interest of China. But the Filipinos will lose. You are not a president of Bato and China. You are the president of the Filipino people.
Lakas-Loob	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An empty threat. • An empty heart. • It's always like this empty threat. • It hurts – for Bato's visa to be cancelled. That's just the first step. <i>Sige nga – tapusin mo.</i> (Go on and finish that.)

Two prominent values contribute to the perception of this issue: the *padrino* system, a Filipino system that utilizes status to skip any due process desired, and *lakas-loob*, a Filipino trait that is synonymous with courage and is defined as a confrontational surface value (Yacat, 2013). Due to these traits and values, people view this issue analytically and see the threats powered by *Lakas Loob* against the opposition as empty and invalid. The *padrino* system also enables the public to see the issue from an angle wherein the president puts his personal relationships and interests above the country. This can be considered “gaming the system,” for it exploits the current system for personal purposes (Bailey et al., 2018). In this case, his relationship with Senator Bato Dela Rosa is a factor that he prioritizes above the possible consequences of terminating the visiting forces agreement (VFA), which is dangerous to the Filipino people.

The study has the goal of identifying Filipino values in political issues on social media that have become viral. After thorough analysis of posts, comments, and viral articles, these are the findings of the study:

1. Filipino Values Reflected in the Viral Political Issues on Social Media – In the issue regarding #SEAGamesFail, the Filipino values are *bahala na* attitude and inconsideration. In Cynthia Villar's issue on rising prices of commodities, the Filipino values that can be seen are inconsideration in the form of *matapobre* as well as passivity. Lastly, in the issue of Bato Dela Rosa's visa cancellation, it is observed that the Filipino values of the *padrino* system, *lakas loob*, and oversensitivity can be seen.

2. Filipino Values in the Viral Political Issue in Terms of Action – Politicians in the #SEAGamesFail issue respond with actions that can be likened to common Filipino values and practices, such as blaming others and *hiya*. The issue of Cynthia Villar's rising prices of commodities shows the common practice of blaming others as well as the *matapobre* mindset. The actions of Duterte and Bato Dela Rosa in the issue regarding Bato Dela Rosa's visa cancellation resonated with the values and practices of the *padrino* system as well as the *mañana* habit.

3. Filipino Values in the Viral Political Issues in Terms of Reaction – Netizens reacted to the #SEAGamesFail political issue and manifested the Filipino values of *hiya* as well as compassion. In another corner, the online masses reacted to Senator Cynthia Villar's statements regarding the rising prices of commodities with the observable Filipino values of inconsideration and *pakikisama*. Lastly, the masses manifested the Filipino values and traits of being fun-loving and *makabayan* in the issue involving Bato Dela Rosa's visa cancellation.

4. Validation of the Filipino Values towards the Message of the Viral Political Issue on Social Media – The message of the issue #SEAGamesFail is strengthened and defined by the influence of the *bahala na* attitude, or the habit of just letting things be, even if they are unfinished or unpolished. In the issue of Senator Cynthia Villar's statements about the rising prices of commodities, the message is highly influenced by the presence of her *matapobre* practices, which are synonymous with inconsideration. Lastly, in the issue of Bato Dela Rosa's visa cancellation, the people's perception regarding the issue refers to two factors: the Filipino values of *lakas loob* as well as the *padrino* system.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings presented, the following conclusions are drawn:

Viral political issues on social media show Filipino values that tend to show a lack of effort, overlook the needs of Filipinos with lesser economic capacity, and portray unnecessary aggressiveness. Politicians portray Filipino values that transfer responsibilities, preserve integrity, and allow them to skip processes.

Netizens oppose such issues and put Filipino values that aim to protect their livelihood, the country's reputation, and the welfare of others. The message of viral political issues is based on what value stands out the most to the public, making it the foundation for the perception and debates around the topic.

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions, the following recommendations are given:

Social media users should be literate and responsible regarding their criticisms of viral political issues on social media. News organizations should adopt a style of writing that can counter aggressiveness and induce sensible responses. Politicians should be responsible for showing Filipino values when they present their identity.

Psychologists may delve into deeper assessment regarding the patterns observed in the responses of the public when it comes to certain values shown and portrayed. Society should gain the skills necessary in order to produce beneficial and appropriate responses that accommodate the situation at hand. Future researchers are encouraged to enhance the study in terms of selecting fresher topics, incorporating various factors, and examining the changes in the existing variables.

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